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Peace-Based Leadership: a Solution to the Presidential Third Term Syndrome

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Abstract

This paper explores the concepts of peace-based leadership as a solution to the presidential third-term syndrome that has become one of the major causes of instability in the developing world. The paper begins by defining peace-based leadership followed by an overview of the countries that have been rocked by third-term syndrome. The paper then focuses on the exploration of the causes and effects of the unconstitutional attempts to run a third-term by presidents. The final part of the paper explores the possibility of adopting peace-based leadership values as a solution. The analysis presented in this paper is informed by Galtung's positive peace theory and Wilber's integral theory also called the All Quadrants, All Levels, All Lines (AQAL) Model.

PEACE-BASED LEADERSHIP: A SOLUTION TO THE PRESIDENTIAL THIRD-TERM SYNDROME

Introduction

In the 21st century, humanity is faced with complex challenges that require urgent attention. In order to effectively deal with these challenges there is need to develop appropriate leadership models which will help society towards attaining a more desirable human condition. Rittel and Webber (1979) describe the challenges faced by modern society as wicked problems which call for a shift in leadership approaches from the hero leader models to models that emphasize on interconnectedness and the building of systemic capacity (Sowcik 2015, p. 59). Peace-based

leadership has gained currency in the emerging discourse of leadership and has been presented as a model of leadership that can be adopted by modern society to deal with complex challenges and build positive peace. This paper identifies the third-term syndrome as one of the wicked or complex challenges facing society today especially in Africa. The paper goes on to present peace-based leadership as a solution to the challenge of the third-term syndrome. The paper makes use of make use of Wilber's integral theory All Quadrants, All Levels, All Lines (AQAL) Model as explained by Miller and Green (2015) to articulate the relevance of peace-based leadership as a solution.

Defining Peace-Based Leadership

The term Peace-based leadership is new in the field of peace, leadership and conflict studies. It is rather problematic to come up with a concrete definition without factoring in the aspects of effective leadership in the concept of peace. Leadership is about convincing or forcing a large group of people to follow and accept one's governance ideas as well producing results purported to benefit the group. Hence peace-based leadership is the ability to convince a large following by mainstreaming peace in governance. Public policing, constitutionalism and governance principles will be peace oriented. Hence it can be agreed that peace enhances good leadership and vice versa (Miller & Green, 2015).

Peace leadership is focused on creating a positive peace, while including essential elements such as working against forces of violence and aggression, or negative peace (Galtung, 1996). It is an integral process to understand individual leadership capacities, relationships with others and representative groups, and the interrelated systems underlying interactions around the world (Wells, 1985). In this respect, peace leadership is much more than, what Einstein referred to as the "mere reduction of violence," as it requires proactive, intentional practices to shift patterns of thinking, knowing, and doing in the face of strongly held beliefs and cherished ways of being, (Green & Miller, 2015).

It is vital to look at the characteristics and roles of peace-based leadership as well as skills and practices that can stimulate peace. Green et al (2015) notes that the purpose of leadership is to promote positive peace hence the leader must be of good morality. Furthermore, the peace-based leaders must utilize the techniques of peaceful governance. This sentiment concurs with the Sane Individual Theory of Peace which posits that for there to be peace in the world people of good morality should occupy leadership positions. This is to avoid psychological deviants from power because they view violence and war as the immediate solution to problems.

Ganz (2010) discusses more on peace-based leadership practices necessary for leading social movements including building relationships; crafting public structures that facilitates peace; providing checks and balances on those with power. Reychler and Stellamans' work on peace building leaders (2005), also reveals some practices and characteristics that define peace-based leaders; these are:

- The ability to come up with strategic approaches to peace including communication,
- Having negotiation, and mediation skills
- The ability to create peaceful and integrated structures
- The willingness to engage in adaptive work

Peace-based leadership as described here is a socially responsible leadership which encompasses concern for others and concern for consequences. Implicit in Reychler and Stallmans' characteristics listed above is the importance of accountability and dependability without which efforts to build sustainable peace are doomed.

Negative and Positive Peace

For one to fully comprehend the meaning of peace-based leadership there is needed to define the term peace. For the purpose of this paper we have decided to adopt Galtung's Negative and positive peace theory as a way of defining peace. The concept was coined by Johan Galtung (1964), and he defines negative peace as the absence of direct violence and war while positive peace is the integration of human society. This therefore shows that negative peace entails the absence of physical, visible direct violence with the presence of structural and cultural violence. On the other hand, positive peace is the absence of violence in any form. Galtung's concept of positive peace is central to the understanding of peace-based leadership. Leadership in this paper is defined as the process of influencing others to understand and agree about what needs to be done and how to do it, and the process of facilitating individual and collective efforts to accomplish shared objectives (Yukl, 2006). In the context of the peace discourse and of this paper a leader is expected to promote inclusive participation and dialogue.

The Evolution of Presidential Term Limits

While term limits date back to classical Greece and Rome, they are a relatively recent innovation in Africa (Dulani, 2011). An examination of 98 presidential-system constitutions enacted in Africa from independence until 1990 shows that only six (South Africa (1961), Comoros (1978), Tanzania (1984), Liberia (1986), Tunisia (1988), and Comoros (1989)) included presidential term-limit clauses. However, the democratic transitions of the 1990s resulted in the popularization and adoption of presidential term limits across the African continent. Out of 64 constitutions adopted or amended between 1990 and 2010, more than three-quarters (49) incorporated tenure limitations. All but one set a maximum of two terms, while Seychelles' set a three-term limit.

Despite the widespread adoption of term limits in the early 1990s, both new and old generations of African leaders continue to seek ways to drop these rules or to identify loopholes that would enable them to remain in power. Across the continent, almost 30 African countries have contemplated the removal of presidential term limits since 1998 (Dulani, 2011). In Eritrea, constitutional term-limit clauses have simply been ignored, and President Isaias Afwerki remains in power after more than 22 years. An attempt by West African leaders in May 2015 to adopt a common position in favor of a maximum of two terms for all presidents in the region failed following disputations from the presidents of Togo (which abolished term limits in 2002) and Gambia.

Methodology

The authors of this paper have opted for a qualitative literature-based research methodology using document analysis of online resources, reports, working papers, discussion papers, scholarly and valid newspaper articles, and books on the topic under study.

Constitutions and Presidential Terms

A major argument in this paper is that the respect for the constitution, particularly by political leaders, is one of the pillars of positive peace. In the 20th century, African continent witnessed a

change in their constitutions in which presidential terms of office were limited. Be that as it may, some African presidents the likes of Yoweri Museveni wanted an indefinite term of office. Such leaders with the support of some scholars argued that limiting presidential term is against the principles of democracy. They argued that one should continue to rule as long as the majority citizens are voting him into office (Namakula, 2016). However, this line of thinking has lost support in the sense that most developing countries' governance has a veneer of democracy yet they are despotic and authoritarian in reality. The presidential term of office limit has been embraced and welcomed as an opportunity for change. Furthermore, electoral processes have failed to bring change and peace because the processes are believed to be manipulated and marred with electoral malpractices (Namakula, 2016).

Many countries placed their hopes on constitutional presidential term limit to bring about change and peace. It has been noted that progressing democracies in Africa, such as Ghana, South Africa and Tanzania embraced and enforced presidential term limits, and subsequently the capacity of supported term limit provisions to facilitate peaceful transfer of power became a core measure of democracy. However, incumbent presidents in some countries like Democratic Republic of Congo, Burundi, Gambia and Congo among others have caused outburst of conflicts and violence by seeking to extend their presidential terms. In such cases, presidents attempt to or succeed in amending the constitutional sections on presidential term limit to allow them a third-term. This has become to be known as a "constitutional coup" (Wilmot, 2015).

Attempts by sitting presidents to temper with constitutions are pure negations of the concept of Peace-based Leadership as described earlier. Peace-based leadership is centered on delivering on the needs and expectations of the governed masses. The next section of this paper presents examples of presidents whose decisions to extend their terms beyond constitutional limits have negatively affected their countries.

Third-Term Syndrome: Case Studies

Third-term syndrome is a disease that has been affecting third world countries' governance systems, infected by their power-hungry leaders who cling on to power. This happens when their term of office constitutionally lapses and they do not pass on the power baton stick but rather they seek another term by amending constitutions. Yoweri Museveni of Uganda appeared to be a peace oriented leader soon after his inauguration in 1986. He was quoted as saying that, "the problem of Africa in general, and Uganda in particular, is not the people but leaders who want to overstay in power." However, in 2005 he failed to live up to his words as he managed to amend the national constitution on the section of presidential term limit allowing himself a third-term in office (Kotze, 2017). In Cameroon Paul Biya has successfully carried out a "constitutional coup" that was allowing only a two term limit. The 1996 supreme law should have prevented him from running for a third-term, but in 2008, infected by the third-term syndrome he revised the constitution to eliminate presidential term limits. It was thought by many political commentators that he is most likely to run again in 2018 (Eze, 2016), and he duly ran and won the elections.

Pierre Nkurunziza of Burundi came into power with many expecting him to be a democratic leader who was going to establish peace through his leadership style guided by good governance principles. The high expectation was based on the fact that Nkurunziza as a former university lecturer would apply rational reasoning in governance for the benefit of the general populace.

Furthermore, he was Burundi's "Minister for Good Governance" that would have moulded him to become a peace-based leader. Nkurunziza with such governance experience was supposed to come up with policies that would uphold the principles of positive peace. This is because his country had been affected by civil war and unrest since independence from Belgium in 1962. In early 1970, Burundi was involved in a serious social protracted conflict between Hutus and Tutsis. It further worsened in 1993 when the first Hutu president, Melchior Ndadaye, was assassinated. This background history prior to his presidency would have inspired him to cultivate peace-based leadership. However, he chose to follow the African trend of leaders who evade constitutions by extending terms of office (Kotze, 2017).

Nkurunziza's argument was that he had not been actually elected the first time; he said he was elected by parliament, so it didn't count. This culminated into violence to the extent that about 300,000 people fled to neighbouring Rwanda and Tanzania, and army generals attempted a coup (Kotze, 2017).

Mr Nkurunziza's CNDD-FDD party scored a widely-expected landslide win in parliamentary polls held on May 29, which were boycotted by the opposition and condemned internationally as neither free nor fair. In 2015 July 21, presidential elections were held, with Mr Nkurunziza defying international condemnation to run for a third-term. The elections were boycotted by the opposition. It was going to take a peace-based leader less effort to know that highly disputed elections are a recipe of direct violence hence stepping down was the option. Therefore, democratic peace thinkers would have judged him correctly and praise him for that decision (Kotze, 2017).

The 2012 presidential election in Senegal was the most controversial, hotly contested and violent in Senegal's democratic history. The incumbent, 85-year-old Abdoulaye Wade, proposed constitutional amendment that would have ensured his success in the next elections by reducing the number of votes needed to win an election. Wade democratically embraced the two-term office limits, but then said that the rule did not apply to him because his first term had begun before the law was passed (Eze, 2016).

The citizens were against president's amendments and took to the streets protesting in the capital. Riots became the order of the day and sensing the danger Wade withdrew the proposal however, continued with his controversial presidential third-term in office. To the surprise of many, he did not rig the polls and was defeated, and conceded after a second round runoff election. But now Mr Wade has said he will remain as head of his party for the 2017 elections "until a new and promising leader is found."

Paul Kagame has effectively ruled Rwanda since the genocide of 1994, which saw 800,000 people massacred in 100 days. He was initially vice president but accepted as de facto ruler; in 2000 he was elected president. The 57-year-old has served the two seven-year terms permitted by the constitution but has remained worryingly ambiguous about his intentions ahead of 2017 elections. And on July 17 parliament voted to support a change in the constitution, allowing him to run again. The opposition are currently attempting to appeal against the vote in the Supreme Court but are struggling to find a lawyer to represent them.

“I belong to the group that doesn’t support change of the constitution,” said Mr Kagame in April. “But in a democratic society, debates are allowed and they are healthy. “I’m open to going or not going depending on the interest and future of this country” (Telegraph, 2015). These statements clearly show that Kagame is not ready to leave office and he view himself as the only person capable of improving the future of Rwanda. These sentiments are not peculiar but are said by most African leaders who do not want to leave power. Therefore, the validity of the rational that African problem is of leadership crisis that lacks peace in its leadership style.

The third-term syndrome has had detrimental effects on the African continent. When leaders overstay in power through manipulating constitutions, the end result is the development of political insecurity in those countries. The toppling and murder of Qaddafi in the Libyan Arab spring in 2011 has led to massive violation of human security, entrenchment of terrorism, the crisis of sovereignty and legitimacy in a once prosperous dictatorial state (Agbelengor, 2017).

Operationalization of the AQAL framework

It is now evident that disrespect for presidential term limits in Africa has generally led to disaster. It has been established from an analysis of the case studies presented above that many conflicts in Africa are caused by leaders who do not want to leave office. Most African leaders defended their move of seeking a third-term in office on the pretext that it does not apply to them because it was introduced during their term of office.

The decision to extend the presidential term stalls a country’s efforts to build positive peace. Such decisions are a sure sign that the leadership is gravitating towards dictatorship. The call for the extension of presidential term is usually characterized by a total disregard of the will of the people and a lack of respect for the constitution which is designed to protect the rights of the people. This stands in sharp contrast to Miller and Green (2015) views on peace-based leadership.

Miller and Green argue that peace leadership involves the mobilization of action for the benefit of society. They further argue that positive peace can be created when a leader is responsive to the needs of the people by enabling them to “live in liberty to their fullest potential, free from the oppression of powers who seek to wield dominance” (Miller & Green, 2015).

Miller and Green in their quest to capture the complex dynamics of peace-based leadership make use of Wilber’s integral theory All Quadrants, All Levels, All Lines (AQAL) Model. The authors of this paper are also convinced that the same framework can be used as a backdrop to the understanding of the dynamics around the third-term syndrome among African leaders.

The AQAL model is presented as a square with four quadrants (see figure 1 on next page). The two quadrants on the left (I and We) represent the interior conditions of a leader both at the individual and community levels. The nature of this quadrant calls leaders to begin with an examination of their readiness to engage peace by determining the degree to which they embody peace themselves. The quadrants at the right (IT and ITS) are the corresponding exterior representations which refers to the leader’s exposure to and use of available knowledge and skills on peace making and peacebuilding. The ITS quadrant describes a leader’s interaction with systems policies and processes which are meant to build peaceful environments. Miller and Green (2015) argue that though presented as separate elements, each process in peace leadership is a part

of a nested and interwoven whole. They further posit that the AQAL model provides a way to hold the whole in consciousness and study the practices needed to bring forward just action.

An AQAL Perspective On Constitution Manipulators

As discussed earlier the AQAL model presents peace-based leadership as a continuum which begins from the inner workings of a person's heart or mind, moving to how the leaders relate and influences and is influenced by the local and global communities.

When one looks at a leader who seeks to extend their term of office beyond the dictates of the constitution one's attention is drawn towards the (I) quadrant which deals with the inner workings of an individual's mind. The individual's mind would most likely be characterized by greed, lack of empathy, selfishness and power hunger. Gaffey (2015) posits that the most obvious factor driving so many African leaders to extend their terms indefinitely is the human desire for authority and prestige. He further argues that many presidents face an uncertain future after leaving office in terms of personal and financial security.

The bottom left quadrant for such a leader is most likely to be characterized by a gulf between the leader's goals and those of the local people. The promotion of factionalist ideas which lead to social fragmentation may be evident. Victimization of opponents to the leader may be achieved through direct violence or structural violence.

The disconnect between the leader and the led which begins in the local community (WE Quadrant) spreads to the global level which is represented by the bottom right quadrant (ITS). The ITS quadrant demonstrates the fact that the leader is no longer building linkages with global systems that seek to promote peace. In many instances the leader will then be regarded as being illegitimate and a liability in the global peacebuilding systems and sub systems. Gaffey (2015) states that some leaders who extend their mandates to govern take advantage of weakness in the global peace and security infrastructure for instance he cites the lack of will by the African Union

to deal with leaders who overstay their constitutional limits. He also argues that AU voices are only loud when there is a military coup.

The top right quadrant (IT) in the case of a rogue leader will show elements of lack of understanding of the real meaning of positive peace. The leader tends to ignore and refuse to tap into the rich traditions of peacebuilding that exist out there as he or she pursues selfish interests. A rogue leader may also demonstrate a lack of peacemaking and conflict resolution skills such as negotiation and mediation. Countries where constitutional coups have occurred have generally been characterized by the absence of the rule of law, distributive justice, absence of civil rights, and absence of basic freedom of individuals (Agbelengor, 2017).

A leader who fits the profile presented above demonstrates a lack of social responsibility. Socially responsible leadership is characterized by elements that include concern for others and concern for consequences. Other elements of socially responsible leadership include accountability and dependability (Sowcik, et al., 2015).

Peace-Based Leadership as a Solution to the Third-Term Syndrome

Through the analysis of the work of the work of Nobel Peace Prize Laureate Dr. Wangari Maathai and the Green Belt Movement (GBM) in Kenya, Miller and Green (2015) are able to use the AQAL model to clearly demonstrate the effectiveness of peace leadership in building positive peace. Dr Wangari was able to build a local movement which addresses issues of poverty and environmental degradation into a formidable peace movement.

Dr Wangari had the internal drive to face a complex challenge facing Kenyan women. She then turned her ideas into action which involved engaging local women into forming a movement around the issue of environmental degradation and poverty. As peace leadership involves engaging the IT quadrant, she then facilitated the training of women in negotiation, mediation and other relevant skills. The GBM was able to influence policy change at the level of the government and as a result of its success it has become a global example of peace leadership in action (Miller & Green, 2015).

A major argument in this paper is that exposure to values and ethics of peace-based leadership can be a panacea to the third-term syndrome that from time to time grips the African continent. A number of leaders have emerged as shining examples of peace-based leadership in Africa and these leaders include Joachim Chissano of Mozambique. He was president from 1986 to 2005. Chissano won the prize for African leadership in 2007 for his leadership qualities and his role in leading his country from conflict to peace and democracy. His work as a mediator in Uganda was also recognized by the Mo Ibrahim Foundation which gave him the award (Mail & Guardian, 2007).

Unlike many other African leaders, Chissano was able to voluntarily step down from office at the end of his term. The decision to leave office and not to pursue a third-term was regarded as a demonstration of Mozambique's democratic maturity.

Other African leaders who were awarded the Ibrahim prize are President Pohamba of Namibia (2014), President Pedro Pires of Cape Verde (2011), President Mogae of Botswana (2008), and

Mandela (2007). In 2016 the foundation failed to find a deserving candidate among the former African presidents (Mo Ibrahim Foundation, 2017).

Peace-based leadership is based on such values as accountability, responsiveness, transparency, empathy and compassion. If these values become entrenched in the leadership culture across the continent sustainable positive peace can be guaranteed.

Conclusion

The paper has argued that the third-term syndrome which has emerged as a serious challenge facing the African continent has brought a lot of suffering to ordinary people. The march towards the attainment of positive peace in a number of countries has been brought to a halt by leaders who have decided to temper with their constitutions in order to extend their terms in office. Wilber's integral theory also called the All Quadrants, All Levels, All Lines (AQAL) Model was used as the basis of discussion of the principles of peace-based leadership. The paper proposed the adoption of the values of peace leadership as a solution to the scourge of the third-term syndrome. The paper provides examples of leaders who have successfully adopted peace-based leadership principles successfully and posits that the presence of such leaders on the continent is a sign that all hope is not lost.

References

- Agbelong, S. (2017). The reluctance to relinquish political power in Africa. *PanAfrican Public Affairs Review*. Retrieved from <https://www.africanexponent.com/bpost/4694-review-of-political-affairs-in-africa>
- Blair, D. (2015). Rwanda's leader joins the African autocrats who rewrite the law to hold power. Retrieved from <https://www.telegraph.co.uk/news/worldnews/africaandindianocean/rwanda/12059442/Rwandas-leader-joins-the-African-autocrats-who-rewrite-the-law-to-cling-to-power.html>
- (n.a.) (2007). Chissano wins \$5M African Leadership prize. (October 22). *The Mail and Guardian*. Retrieved from <https://mg.co.za/article/2007-10-22-chissano-wins-5m-african-leadership-prize>
- Dulani, B. (2011). Personal rule and presidential term limits in Africa. Unpublished PhD Thesis, Michigan State University.
- Einstein, A. (2011). *Einstein on peace*. New York, NY: Random House.
- Eze, K. (2016). The efficacy of presidential term limits in Africa. MINDS Annual African Youth Dialogue 2016 Discussion Paper.
- Gaffey, C. (2015) Africa's Third-Term Problem: Why Leaders Keep Clinging to Power <http://www.newsweek.com/africa-third-term-problem-cling-power-403440>
- Galtung, J. (1996). *Peace by Peaceful Means: Peace and Conflict, Development, and Civilization*. Los Angeles, CA: Sage Publications.
- Ganz, M. (2010). Leading Change: Leadership, Organization, and Social Movements. In Nitin N. & Rakesh K. (eds.) *Handbook of Leadership Theory and Practice*. Cambridge, MA: Harvard Business Press.
- Grewal, B. S. (2003). *Johan Galtung: Positive peace and negative peace*. Auckland University.
- Kotze, J. S. (2017). Africa faces new threat to its democracy: The 'constitutional coup' aka 'third-term tragedy' <https://www.news24.com/Africa/News/africa-faces-a-new-threat-to-democracy-the-constitutional-coup-20170209> Accessed 3 October 2017

- Miller, W. M. & Green, Z. G. (2015). An integral perspective of peace leadership. *Integral Leadership Review*, 15(2), pp. 1-10
https://digitalcommons.chapman.edu/education_articles/85/
- Mo Ibrahim Foundation. (2017). Mo Ibrahim Foundation announces no winner of 2016 Ibrahim Prize for Achievement in African Leadership, Retrieved from
<http://mo.ibrahim.foundation/news/2017/mo-ibrahim-foundation-announces-no-winner-2016-ibrahim-prize-achievement-african-leadership/>
- Namakula C. S. (2016). The efficacy of presidential term limits in Africa. MINDS Annual African Youth Dialogue 2016 Discussion Paper.
- Reychler, L. and Stellamans, A. (2004). Researching Peace Building Leadership. Paper presented at the Conflict Resolution and Peace Building Commission (CRPB) at the International Peace Research Association in Sopron, Hungary, July.
- Wells, L. Jr. (1985). The group-as-whole perspective and its theoretical roots. In Colman, A.D. & Geller, M.H. (Eds.), *Group relations reader 2*, (pp. 109–126). Washington, DC: A. K Rice Institute.
- Wilmot, C. (2015). Africa: How and why term limits matter. Retrieved from
<http://africanarguments.org/2015/10/05/how-and-why-term-limits-matter/>
- Sowick, M., Andenoro, A. C., McNutt, M. & Murphy, S. E. (2015). *Leadership 2050-Critical Challenges, Key Context and emerging Trends; Building Leadership Bridges*. New York, NY: Emerald Group Publishing.